

DESIGN OF IMPACT DAMAGE TOLERANT COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: In this paper, the effect of laminate stacking sequence on compression strength after impact of a T300/5405(BMI) composite were studied. Failure stresses and strains as a function of stacking sequence are governed by three parameters defined by effective elastic moduli. The optimisation of these three parameters is very useful to damage tolerant composite laminate design. Moreover, a high in-plane shear modulus skin concept is proposed. It is more reasonable than the so-called low stiffness skin concept for damage tolerant composite stiffened panel design. The $\pm 45^\circ$ kevlar and glass fibre plies coated on carbon fibre reinforced laminates can offer superior impact resistance and raise compression strength after impact.

KEYWORDS: impact damage, impact resistance, compression strength after impact, in-plane stress concentration, in-plane shear modulus, impact damage tolerance design

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials subjected to impact may suffer a significant loss in compression strength. Impact damage arises on composite aircraft structures due to dropped loads and runway debris etc. In order to overcome impact threat and to provide composite aircraft structural integrity, the impact damage tolerance aspect must be introduced into the initial sizing criteria during structural layout, i.e. the method to determine required thickness and lay-ups [1]. At present, only the limited amount of work has concentrated on effect of laminate stacking sequence on impact resistance and, especially compression strength after impact (CAI).

In this paper, a systematic study was conducted on above mentioned issues for a carbon fibre/BMI composite.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material

A carbon fibre/BMI T300/5405 composite was used in this study. Laminates of 4 different number of plies (15-, 35-, 37-, and 53-ply), 31 different lay-ups of 0° -, $\pm 45^\circ$ -, 90° -plies were tested and evaluated, including fifteen 15-ply, fifteen 35-ply, two 37-ply and one 53-ply laminates denoted by [x% 0° : y% $\pm 45^\circ$: z% 90°]. Among these, two 37-ply laminates are

identical to a 35-ply laminate with a lay-up of [30:60:10] coated respectively with $\pm 45^\circ$ kevlar fibre plies and glass fibre plies.

Impact Tests

Specimens were impacted by a free-falling steel impactor with a hemispherical end of 1-inch-diameter. The specimens of 15-, 35- and 53-ply were impacted with energy of 14J, 47J and 93J. Since two 37-ply laminates have different thickness, their values of impact energy were respectively 58.6J and 56.1J which were calculated from energy per unit thickness of the 35-ply laminate. During impact, the specimens were clamped between two steel plates with a central rectangular opening whose centre was aligned with those of the specimens and the impactor. The impactor was captured after impact to prevent secondary strikes. After impact the specimens were inspected by a penetrant enhanced X-radiography. Dent depths were measured with a micrometer.

Compression Tests

Compression test fixture includes upper and lower load introduction devices and anti-buckling guides. The load introduction devices are similar to those of NASA RP 1142. Two stiffened thin steel plates with a central opening of 60 mm diameter were designed to prevent global buckling of the specimens. They are very effective for compression tests of thinner specimens. In order to reduce the friction between the anti-buckling plates and the specimens, their contact surfaces were separated with Teflon.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Compressive Failure Stresses and Strains after Impact

Laminates with Constant Percentages of $\pm 45^\circ$ -Plies

Figure 1 displays trends of failure stresses and strains as a function of 0° -ply share for impacted 15- and 35-ply laminates. The failure stress increases with the increase of the percentage of 0° -plies. The failure strain in figures 1(a) and 1(c) initially decreases and then increases, i.e. exhibits concave curves. While the failure strain in figures 1(b) and 1(d) monotonically decreases as the percentage of 0° -plies increases. The two concave curves are due to high failure strains of the two laminates corresponding to the last points in figures 1(a) and 1(c). Measured data shows these two laminates have much smaller dent depths than others, indicating a very small number of fibre breakages in them. The high strains may be caused by very small dent depths of the two laminates. If damage sizes of these two laminates were identical to those of other laminates in figure 1, a drop in failure strain would be expected to be significant, yielding monotonically decreasing trends. This will be further discussed later.

Laminates with Constant Percentages of 0° -Plies

Figure 2 displays trends of failure stresses and strains as a function of $\pm 45^\circ$ -ply share for impacted 15- and 35-ply laminates. Both failure stress and strain increase as the percentage of $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies increases.

Fig. 1 Failure stress and strain vs % 0° of laminates with constant % $\pm 45^\circ$

Fig. 2 Failure stress and strain vs % $\pm 45^\circ$ of laminates with constant % 0°

Laminates with Constant Percentages of 90° Plies

Figure 3 shows trends of failure stress and strain as a function of ±45° -ply share for impacted 15- and 35-ply laminates. As the percentage of ±45° -plies increases, the failure stress increases while the failure strain decreases.

Fig. 3 Failure stress and strain vs %± 45° of laminates with constant % 90°

Governing Factors of Compression Strength after Impact

Stress Concentrations Due to Impact Damage

The failure strength of a damaged laminate strongly depends on damage induced stress concentrations. As well known, the stress concentration due to holes in orthotropic materials depends on their elastic constants. For example, a central hole in a infinite width orthotropic laminate generates a stress concentration [2] of

$$K_t = 1 + \sqrt{2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_y}{E_x} - \nu_{yx}} + \frac{E_y}{2G_{xy}} \right)}$$

where E_y , E_x , G_{xy} and ν_{yx} are the effective laminate normal moduli, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively, and the respective y and x are parallel and transverse to the loading direction.

In-plane and out-of-plane stresses redistribute around impact damage due to changes in local stiffness which may occur due to fibre failure and/or sublaminar instability. It is believed that the stress concentration is a key factor affecting compression strength after impact of a laminate [3].

The stress concentration type which is dominant for impacted laminate failure must be identified. It can be done with an understanding of compression failure modes of impacted laminates, i.e. separating the critical growth modes from those that occur as a consequence of laminate failure [4]. Extensive experimental work on damage response and growth modes during compression tests of impacted laminates indicated that, both brittle and tough materials exhibit delamination growth at time very close to the final failure. In other words, the delamination growth and the final failure are nearly simultaneous. Moreover, observations show that the delamination growth only occurs near the non-impacted surface of a laminate. The delamination growth near the impacted surface of the laminate is a consequence of the final failure. It seems to be that the delamination growth near the non-impacted surface has no ability to cause the final failure of the laminate. Experimental observations show that the final failure is dominated by local post-buckling of all sublaminae as a whole. This kind of post-buckling effectively reduces local stiffness, which increases the in-plane stress concentration. As the in-plane stress concentration is increased to a critical value, it leads to the failure of the laminate. In addition, post-failure patterns of impacted laminates show a typical shear-crippling failure mode except two buckled surface sublaminae. This further verifies the governing role of the in-plane stress concentration in compression failure of impacted laminates.

The serious fibre failure can largely change the local stiffness and causes a significant increase of the in-plane stress concentration. Consequently the compression strength after impact is largely reduced by the serious fibre failure. Evidently, the major cause of the concave curves in figures 1(a) and 1(c) are the very low extent of fibre failure in the two laminates corresponding to the last points in figures 1(a) and 1(c). The impact induced fibre failure has a large effect on the compression strength after impact.

Characterisation of Compressive Failure Stresses and Strains after Impact

As is the case for holes, one can link compression strength after impact with the in-plane stress concentration or elastic modulus. It may be an effective way to get a deep insight into the influence of lay-ups on compression strength after impact. Insight gained from the stress concentration formula of holes leads to an attempt of correlating three parameters

$$\alpha_1 = \sqrt{\frac{E_y}{E_x} - \nu_{yx}} + \frac{E_y}{2G_{xy}}$$

$$\alpha_2 = \frac{E_y}{E_x}$$

$$\alpha_3 = G_{xy}$$

with compression stresses and strains after impact.

Figure 4 shows the failure strain versus the parameter α_1 for all the 15- and 35-ply laminates respectively. It is seen that the failure strain increases as α_1 decreases. But the failure stress is not uniformly consistent with α_1 . It strongly depends on the parameter α_2 . The higher the modulus of elasticity in the loading direction compared to that transverse to it, the higher is the failure stress, as shown in figure 5. But the failure strain can not be characterised by α_2 .

Fig. 4 Failure strain vs parameter α_1

Fig. 5 Failure stress vs parameter α_2

As was indicated above, in the case of constant percentages of 90° - or 0° -plies, the failure strain increases with the increase of $\pm 45^\circ$ -ply share. By linking the failure strain with the stiffness in the loading direction, it is found that, in the case of constant percentage of 90° -plies, the failure strain increases with the decrease of the stiffness in the loading direction. This forms a base of the so-called ‘low stiffness skin’ concept for design of impact damage tolerant composite stiffened panels. In the case of constant percentage of 0° -plies, however, the stiffness in the loading direction is nearly unchangeable. In this case, one can not correlate the failure strain with stiffness in the loading direction. But in both cases, it is found that the failure strain increases with the increase of in-plane shear modulus, G_{xy} . Figure 6 is the trends of failure strain versus in-plane shear modulus, G_{xy} .

In the case of constant percentages of $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies, as the percentage of 0° -plies increases, the in-plane shear modulus is unchangeable while the stiffness in the loading direction increases. Therefore, the failure strain decreases with the increase of the stiffness in the loading direction.

Design of Impact Damage Tolerant Composite Laminates

The 'low stiffness skin' or 'soft skin' concept has been successfully used in design of the damage tolerant composite panels. This design incorporates a low stiffness skin with a predominance of $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies and a low percentage of 0° -plies. The low stiffness skin is damage tolerant to high strains. The primary axial load-carrying reinforcement, that is, 0° fibres, is concentrated at the stiffeners.

Based on the above discussion of the governing factors of compression strength after impact, a 'high in-plane shear modulus skin' concept is proposed. The new concept is more reasonable than the old one because a laminate with a higher in-plane shear modulus has higher ability to redistribute load from damaged to undamaged areas than a laminate with a lower shear modulus. $\pm 45^\circ$ -ply share is a key factor in design of impact damage tolerant stiffened panels of aircraft. Generally, a damage tolerant to high strain laminate can be achieved by increasing $\pm 45^\circ$ -ply share. But the laminate with a predominance of $\pm 45^\circ$ -plies and a low percentage of 0° -plies is damage tolerant to high strains but not to high stresses.

It should be emphasised that this approach is much less attractive for a skin which is a axial load-carrying element. For example, it is effective for a thick wing, but it is much less attractive for a thin wing, where it is more efficient to keep primary load-carrying material near the outer surface for great effectiveness in bending. Therefore, it is more attractive and desirable to design a laminate which is damage tolerant not only to high strains but also to high stresses. It can be done by choosing stacking sequences with low α_1 , high α_2 and high G_{xy} . Of course, there exists a match of these three parameters. For instance, among the laminates of this study, stacking sequences of [20:67:13] of 15-ply and [20:69:10] of 35-ply laminates satisfy the above requirement of low α_1 , high α_2 and high G_{xy} and are comparably damage tolerant to both high strains and stresses.

It should be noted that, in selection of the damage tolerant laminates, the requirement of low impact resistance should be considered. A combination of the low impact resistance and the above design method will leads to an excellent impact damage tolerant laminate design.

Impact Resistance and Compression Strength after Impact of Laminates Coated with $\pm 45^\circ$ Kevlar or Glass Fibre Plies

Two 37-ply laminates (denoted by L_k and L_g) are identical to the 35-ply laminate with a lay-up of [30:60:10] (denoted by L) coated respectively with $\pm 45^\circ$ kevlar fibre plies and glass fibre plies. Since these three laminates have different thickness, an identical impact energy per unit thickness was used, as mentioned above.

The $\pm 45^\circ$ kevlar and glass fibre plies coated on carbon fibre reinforced laminates greatly decrease impact induced fibre breakages and cause very small dents, as shown in figure 7. Therefore, the $\pm 45^\circ$ kevlar and glass fibre plies effectively improve the impact resistance of carbon fibre reinforced composites.

Fig. 6 Failure strain vs in-plane shear modulus G_{xy}

Fig. 7 Sizes of impact damage

Fig. 8 Compression strength after impact

Due to very small dent depths of the two 37-ply laminates, they show much higher post-impact strengths than the 35-ply laminate, as show in figure 8. Since the test data shows no significant differences in damage areas, the high increase of the strength is obviously caused by the low extent of the fibre breakage. Because the fibre breakage can largely reduce the local stiffness and enhance the in-plane stress concentration, it strongly affects compression strength after impact.

Damage areas are commonly used to characterise impact damage while dent depths are hardly considered. Without analysis to link the dent depth with the impact damage, compression strength as a function of damage area may be misleading in some cases. The impact damage must be characterised by both damage area and dent depth.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The most important conclusion drawn from the study is that the failure stress and strain after impact are strongly affected by the in-plane stress concentration and their trends as a function of lay-ups are governed by three parameters defined by effective elastic moduli. The optimisation of these three parameters is very useful to damage tolerant composite laminate design. A high in-plane shear modulus skin concept is proposed. It is more reasonable than the so-called low stiffness skin concept for damage tolerant composite stiffened panel design. The $\pm 45^\circ$ kevlar and glass fibre plies effectively improve the impact resistance of carbon fibre reinforced composites.

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